

HWO Instrument Concept Studies Workshop

Initial Information Document

HWO TMPO Systems Engineering Team

May 4, 2026

H A B I T A B L E
W R L D S
O B S E R V A T O R Y

The logo for the Habitable Worlds Observatory (HWO) is located in the bottom-right corner. It consists of the words "HABITABLE", "WORLDS", and "OBSERVATORY" stacked vertically in a light blue, spaced-out, sans-serif font. A stylized white symbol, resembling a crescent moon or a partial orbit, is positioned between the "W" and "R" of "WORLDS".

Acknowledgement

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With inputs from CI, HWI, and UVI Working Group teams	

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Document Outline

- **Introduction**
- **Mission and Observatory Overview**
- **EAC5 Observatory Design Guidelines and Concept**
- **Instrument Mass, Power, and Volume Allocations**
- **Preliminary Interface Assumptions: Mechanical, Structural, Thermal, and Electrical**
- **Telescope and Instruments**
 - EAC-5 Telescope Optical Design
 - Instrument Design Guidelines (Government Team Response to EAC-5 Instrument Capabilities)
 - Coronagraph Instrument (CI) NIR Channel
 - High Resolution Imager (HRI)
 - Guiding Design Guidelines
 - HRI-S WFS Design Guidelines
 - Ultraviolet Multi-Object Spectrograph (UV MOS)
 - Ultraviolet Integral Field Unit (UV IFU)

Introduction

The Initial Information Document provides top-level information on the HWO mission, Exploratory Analytic Case-5 (EAC-5), instrument resource allocations, and instrument interfaces to support instrument studies.

- **Current Design Basis**

- Derived from the HWO Technology Maturation Project Office (TMPO) EAC-5 design
- Large aperture: 8.2 m inscribed diameter / 10.0 m circumscribed diameter

- **Guiding Principles for Specified Resources and Interfaces**

- Intended as a guide, not strict requirements; allocations may vary as EAC architectures evolve
- Resource allocations (mass, power, volume) and interface constraints are preliminary; compliance is encouraged but some exceedances may be considered

- **HWO TMPO encourages instrument proposers to identify:**

- Guidelines that are challenging or easily met with margin
- Missing guidelines that may impact the design
- Opportunities and breakpoints in allocations and interface assumptions
- Trades against allowable resources and interface assumptions are encouraged

Instrument Capabilities

The candidate instrument capabilities within scope of this study are listed below. Other instrument capabilities not listed here may be within the scope, if the study convincingly demonstrates sufficient traceability to HWO science goals.

- **Coronagraphy (*see note below):**
 - Near-IR coronagraphic imaging and spectroscopy
 - Near-UV coronagraphic imaging
- **Spectroscopy:**
 - UV / visible integral field spectroscopy
 - UV / visible multi-object spectroscopy
- **Imaging:**
 - High-resolution near-UV / visible / near-IR imaging
 - Visible wavelength high-precision astrometry
 - Observatory guiding and wavefront sensing

Note that visible coronagraphic imaging and spectroscopy are excluded from this study, as the visible coronagraph is being designed as directed work within HTMPO.

Instrument & Guider Assembly for Instrument Studies

- The observatory accommodates a total of six instrument bays for science instruments and guiders.
- **Instrument Location Guidelines**
 - **CI NIR Channel:** Positioned on the cold side of the observatory to enable passive cooling of detectors
 - **Instrument A (w/ far UV):** Located under CI bay to minimize number of reflections
 - **All Other Instruments and Guiders:** May be located in any of the remaining instrument bays (B–E) or across multiple bays

Habitable Worlds Observatory (HWO) Mission Overview

- **NASA's next flagship mission, recommended by the Astro2020 Decadal Survey**
 - Large-aperture UV/Optical/NIR observatory performing transformative astrophysics across cosmic time
 - First telescope designed to directly image and characterize Earth-like exoplanets, including search for signs of life
- **HWO includes a segmented primary mirror and coronagraph instrument**
- **Operational orbit at Sun-Earth L2**
- **Serviceable at L2**

Exploratory Analytic Cases (EACs)

Mission architectures developed to explore the HWO trade space:

- Explore key architectural options and breakpoints to guide future point design decisions
- Develop end-to-end models and tools to understand modeling capabilities and needs
- Identify technology gaps and guide maturation of potential solutions
- Provide early feedback to launch vehicle vendors to help influence their direction

We don't expect any of the cases studied will become a baseline design going forward. These are only intended to explore and practice.

Early JWST

Final JWST
CML 9+

EACs Design Guidelines

- Baffle/barrel protection for optics against micrometeoroid impacts
- Compatible with at least two future launchers
- Serviceable architecture
- ULE glass mirrors (primary/secondary) at room temperature for simplified I&T
- Field-of-Regard: $\pm 45^\circ$ pitch, $\pm 22.5^\circ$ roll, 360° yaw
- Slew/Settle: 90° in 60 min
- Observatory LOS stability: 4 mas
- Passive cooling for NIR detectors
 - Active cooling is permitted for consideration within the scope of this study

NASA
Space Launch System

SpaceX
Starship

Blue Origin
New Glenn
(7x2 shown, 9x4 considered)

Observing Zone

- $45^\circ - 135^\circ$ off Sun Line
- 360° about Sun Line
- $\pm 22.5^\circ$ about Line of Sight (LOS) off max power roll angle

HWO Observatory Schematic

Overall Approach to EAC 4 and 5

- **EAC-4 Objectives:**

- Balances cost, schedule, and science performance
- Mitigate baffle-related engineering risks

EAC-4: To be delivered as part of the **HWO Technical Packet** at the kick-off meeting

- **EAC-5 Objectives:**

- Driven by science goals with minimum 8-m inscribed diameter aperture
- Consider large flat sunshade to improve thermal stability

EAC-4 selection pending

- **Instrument Suite:**

- CI (VIS, 'Bridge', NIR)
- UV MOS and UV IFU
- HRI (provides guiding and out-of-field WFS)
- Reserved bay for future servicing mission instrument

EAC-5: Delivered as part of the **Instrument Study Technical Information Packet**

EAC5 Observatory Overview: Front View

EAC5 Overview: Rear View *(radiators, OTE closeout not shown)*

EAC5 Overview: Telescope to SI light paths

EAC5 Instrument & Guider Assembly Overview *(radiators not shown)*

EAC5 Sunshade

Large flat sunshade precludes solar impingement on SI radiators over FOR ($\pm 45^\circ$ pitch, $\pm 22.5^\circ$ roll)

Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
AOS	- Aft Optics System
BDA	- Baffle Deployment Assembly
BG	- Beyond Gravity
BSF	- Backplane Support Frame
CAD	- Computer Aided Design
CFRP	- Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer
CGI	- CoronaGraph Instrument (Roman)
CI	- Coronagraph Instrument
CCS	- Coronagraph Coordinate System
DBS	- Deployable Baffle Subsystem
DRSA	- Deployed Radiator Shade Assembly
EAC	- Exploratory Analytic Case
EGSE	- Electrical Ground Support Equipment
GI-A	- Guider Instrument A
GI-B	- Guider Instrument B
HGAS	- High Gain Antenna System
HRI	- High Resolution Imager
HS	- HardShell (EAC4)
IFS	- Integral Field Spectrograph
IGA	- Instrument & Guider Assembly (IGA)
IMS	- Instrument Module Structure
IRP	- Instrument Radiator Panels
IRU	- Inertial Reference Unit
ISS	- International Space Station
JWST	- James Webb Space Telescope
LRM	- Launch Restraint Mechanism
LUVUIR	- Large UltraViolet Optical InfraRed Telescope
LV	- Launch Vehicle

Acronym	Definition
MBA	- Main Baffle Assembly
MMOD	- MicroMeteoroids and Orbital Debris
NG	- New Glenn
OBS	- Observatory
OTE	- Optical Telescope Element
PAC	- Payload Aft Closeout
PAS	- Payload Adapter System
PLF	- Payload Fairing
PM	- Primary Mirror
PMBA	- Primary Mirror Backplane Assembly
PMSA	- Primary Mirror Segment Assemblies
PSS	- Payload Sunshade
ROSA	- Roll-Out Solar Array
RSS	- Radiator Sunshade
SAA	- Solar Array Assembly
SCB	- Spacecraft Bus
SCE	- Spacecraft Element
SLS	- Space Launch System
SM	- Secondary Mirror
SMA	- Secondary Mirror Assembly
SMSS	- Secondary Mirror Support Structure
SS	- Sun Shield
ST	- Star Tracker
ULE	- UltraLow Expansion
USG	- US Government
UVI	- UV Instrument
VPM	- Vertical Primary Mirror (EAC4)
XI	- Extra Instrument

Instrument Mass Allocation Guidelines

- **Current Best Estimate (CBE)**
 - Note: based on Observatory “allocation” of 25000kg CBE
- **Includes:**
 - Internal Harnesses
 - Thermal control (passive and active)
 - Radiators
 - Insulation
 - Coolers
 - Etc.
 - Avionics
 - *Note: data storage provided by Spacecraft*
- **Does not include:**
 - All growth and SI margins are held at the project level
 - GFE latches SI-side (operational and launch restraints)
 - GFE servicing grapple fixture
 - GFE servicing electrical connectors SI-side

Instrument	CBE Mass (kg)
CI-NIR*	150
A (w/ far UV)	500
B	350
C	350
D	200
E	200

*Optics, mechanisms, electronics, and harnesses (see CI section for details)

Instrument Volume Allocation Guidelines

- **Not to exceed (NTE)**
 - Clearance to surrounding IMS guaranteed if SI stowed frequency $\geq 40\text{Hz}$
- **Includes on SI side:**
 - Radiator
 - MLI
 - Carve-outs for light pass-through(s) and avoidances
 - Avionics
 - Active thermal control/cooler if needed
 - Clearance for installation/removal on orbit
 - Grapple fixture accommodation
- **Does not include:**
 - Bridging structure to latches SI-side (operational)
- **Note: deploying radiator not permitted**
 - NASA open to discussion

Instrument	Detailed Volume Descriptions
CI-NIR	Slide 35
A (w/ far UV)	Slide 43
B	Slide 53
C	Slide 55
D	Slide 62
E	Slide 66

Power Budget

Item	Power (W)	Notes
Coronagraph Instrument – NIR Channel	252	See CI NIR section for details.
Instrument A	525	Top-down estimates; allocations subject to revision based on study feedback.
Instrument B	250	
Instrument C	250	
Instrument D	200	
Instrument E	200	
Instrument Total	1677	

Latch position; degrees of restrain (DOR) details on IMS

CI interfaces:
2 / 2 / 2 / 2 DOR
(pairs in-line)

SI's with kinematic
interfaces: 1 each of

- 1 DOR
- 2 DOR
- 3 DOR

Interfaces to IMS: Mechanical

- **For SI's except CI-NIR:**

- Operational: kinematic mount to metering plane also used by primary mirror consisting of 3 serviceable interfaces:
 - 3 degrees of restraint (DOR)
 - 2 DOR
 - 1DOR
- Launch supplemental (for SI's except CI) to relieve cantilever launch loads:
 - 1 DOR vertical
 - 1 DOR lateral
- GFE SI-side of interfaces

- **For CI-NIR (new channel built on CI structures provided by NASA/JPL) 3 DOR**

- Note: main CI uses four x 2 DOR restraints on side rails (not directly @ metering plane of PM)
- See CI section for additional details

- **Assuming kinematic interfaces, SI fundamental modes ≥ 40 Hz**

- **CG Launch load factors $\sim 12g$ per axis for primary structure**

- Evaluate one axis at a time
- Cantilever is relieved for launch by supplemental supports
- Load factors for internal components per Mass Acceleration Curve (available upon request)

Instrument Thermal Interfaces

- **Instrument Bays (5 sides of the enclosure)**
 - Volume: See mechanical
 - Temperature: Room temperature
- **Instrument to IMS:**
 - IMS will be blanketed (either at the truss or cavity level)
 - Minimize heat exchange to IMS
 - **Conductive Interface:** Instrument should assume isolative hardware/flexures
 - Estimated conductance: 0.05W/K per latch (similar to HST)
 - See mechanical for # of connections/latches
 - Consider using Ti hardware
 - **Radiative Interface:** Instrument should radiatively isolate from the IMS
 - Will be desirable, especially with low temperature components

Instrument Radiators

- **Available Area:**
 - Ensure servicing grapple feature is accounted for
 - Plan to subdivide radiator area into desired temperature zones
- **Views to Space (EAC5 Specific):**
 - Estimated blackbody IR sink temperature calculated and provided based on latest EAC5 geometry
 - IR backloading from sun shade is accounted for
 - No solar loading → can optimize for high ϵ radiator coatings
- **Radiators for cold components:**
 - May have fewer options for heat spreading → limits for heat pipe working fluids → may require high purity metallic spreaders
 - Smaller ΔT^4 to their blackbody sink temperature → more radiator area will be required
- **NOTE: assumptions and guidelines are consistent with the EAC5 design and are subject to change given the early state of HWO design**

EAC5 Sink Temp Range Across All Attitudes

Avionics Block Diagram

- **Efforts are underway to standardize interfaces across all instruments; leading options include:**
 - SpaceWire — well-established with extensive heritage
 - Ethernet — higher overhead but potentially more advantageous for instrument development and EGSE
- **Interfaces under consideration:**
 - Command, Telemetry, and Science Data to spacecraft/recorder
 - Avionics and heater power
 - Analog temperature readings (if required when instrument power is off)

HWO TMPO Optical Telescope Design

Design Assumptions & Guidelines

Optical Design Team: Joe Howard, Mike Rodgers, Jon Papa, Hong Tang, Guangjun Gao,
Len Seals, James Corsetti, Scott Rohrbach, Breann Sitarski

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EAC5 Telescope Design Specifications

Telescope Specification	Range	EAC5	Comment
Pupil obstruction	none	none	CI high contrast imaging performance
Entrance Pupil Diameter (EPD), m	maximize	10	Launch vehicle payload volume
Inscribed Circular Pupil Diameter (D), m	>6	8.2	CI minimum required for science
Focal Length, m	-	171	UVI MOS MSA hardware and science
F/#	>10	19	UVI MOS MSA hardware structure depth
Maximum delta Angle of Incidence, deg	minimize	11.1	CI needs to minimize polarization aberrations
<u>Fields of View</u>			
CI, arcmin ²	-	0.001	2x2 arcsec for acquisition
Instrument A, arcmin ²	-	9	3x3 arcmin field to MSA for EAC-5
Instrument B, arcmin ²	-	6	3' x 2'
Instrument C, arcmin ²	-	12	3' x 4'
Instrument D, arcmin ²	-	0.003	3 x 3 arcsec
Instrument E, arcmin ²	-	1	1x1 arcmin
Total Field of View:		58.004	

CI = Coronagraph Instrument

Notional Field Layout for EAC 5, (loosely scaled)

Optical Design Summary

- **The HWO telescope optical design is highly constrained by the instrument design guidelines of the CI and UVI MOS.**
- **The rocket fairing size also constrains the telescope aperture and secondary mirror distance due to the volumetric limits.**
- **Instrument etendue (specifically the desired field of view) plays a significant role in realizable instrument level packaging for the wider field instruments (i.e. HRI and UVI MOS).**
- **Freeform Optics enables more science for HWO.**

Government EAC-5 Instrument Design Overview

- Coronagraph Instrument (CI)
 - Visible and near-infrared channels
 - High-contrast imaging + spectroscopy
 - Heritage from Roman's CGI
- High-Resolution Imager (HRI)
 - Near-ultraviolet/optical/near-infrared high resolution imager
 - Low-spectral resolution spectroscopy is possible with prisms + gratings
 - Astrometry mode
 - Guiding and telescope wavefront sensing + control
- Ultraviolet multi-object spectrograph (UVMOS)
 - Far-ultraviolet/near-ultraviolet/optical wide-field, multi-object spectrograph
 - High spectral resolution point source spectroscopy (FUV/NUV)
- Ultraviolet Integral Field Spectrograph (UVIFS)
 - Far-ultraviolet/near-ultraviolet spatially resolved spectroscopy

Science Instrument Dimensions

- **Overall dimensions (orthogonal views)**
 - Provide STEP file referencing Optics coordinate system upon request
- **Position of SI w/r to Optics coordinate axes (center of PM)**
- **Proposed local SI coordinate system**
- **Optical input physical location w/r to SI**
 - Position
 - Opening dimensions
 - Reference chief ray of optical path into SI
 - Reference optical path positions where other SI's pass through or around
- **Positions of operational Interfaces to IMS with depiction of DOR (degrees of restraint for each)**
- **Positions of additional conceptual launch Interfaces to IMS door with depiction of DOR (degrees of restraint for each)**
- **Details of radiator dimensions showing “cutouts” for servicing interface and door interfaces, with calculated remaining actual radiative area available**

HWO TMPO Coronagraph Instrument (CI)

Near Infrared (NIR) Channel Study
Design Assumptions & Guidelines

HWO TMPO CI Team

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Assumptions & Guidelines

● Configuration Assumptions:

- Proposed NIR channel optics will be mounted on a shared optical bench alongside a USG-provided 'bridge' Channel (same side of bench) and a USG-provided VIS Channel on the opposite side of the bench.
- Proposed NIR channel electronics and harness will be mounted on a shared, thermally controlled electronics pallet located approx. 1 m from the optical bench.
- Proposed NIR channel thermal control will be provided by a shared thermal management system using heaters, blankets and/or enclosures, a room-temperature radiator, and a cryogenic-temperature radiator.

● Accommodation Guidelines (preliminary):

1. Volume

- 2.0m x 1.3m x 0.4m; horizontal mounting area is 2.0m x 1.3m; vertical height is 0.4m.

2. Mass

- 150 kg; includes proposed NIR channel optics, mechanisms, and harnesses (e.g. items on the optical bench)
- Does not include shared optical bench, shared thermal hardware, DM electronics, or shared housekeeping electronics

3. Power

- 250 W dissipating to shared 293K room temp radiator
- 0.85 W dissipating to shared 100K cryogenic radiator
- 0.4 W dissipating to shared 65K cryogenic radiator

Assumptions & Guidelines, continued...

● Additional notes:

1. Optical

- The NIR coronagraph coordinate system (CCS_{NIR}), input beam location, and pupil image are shown in the following figures. The input starlight is a collimated beam with direction $(0.8829, 0.4695, 0.0)$ in the CCS_{NIR} , and forms an image of the telescope entrance pupil centered at $(538.8, 273.7, 105.5)$ in millimeters. The circumscribed diameter of the PM pupil is 10 m, and the diameter of the largest inscribed circle on the primary mirror is 8.2 m. The inscribed diameter at the PM maps to a 40 mm diameter circle at the NIR coronagraph entrance pupil.
- We expect a fine steering mirror (FSM) to be the first optic in the instrument, at that pupil image.

2. Structural

- The optical bench is a 0.4m thick carbon graphite structure with metallic inserts for mounting optics and proximity electronics. NIR channels share one side of the structure, and a VIS channel is located on the opposite side.

3. Thermal

- Both sides of the optical bench (VIS and NIR) will be maintained at 293K via heaters, blankets, and a radiator.
- Cryogenic thermal control to 65K-100K is provided via a separate radiator located within 0.5m of NIR cameras.

4. Electronics

- VIS and NIR channel electronics boxes are mounted on the thermally controlled electronics pallet.
- Shared housekeeping/infrastructure electronics (e.g., C&DH, PCD) are also located on the electronics pallet.

5. ***NOTE: assumptions and guidelines are consistent with the EAC5 design and are subject to change given the early state of HWO design.***

Initial CI Specifications

Input optics	Collimated input beam as shown in following pages		
	Inscribed beam diameter at entrance pupil	mm	40
	Reflections before coronagraph entrance	-	11
Broad-band Imager	Wavelength range	micron	1.0-1.7
	Inner Working Angle	λ/D	≤ 3
	Outer Working Angle	λ/D	≥ 20
	Typical observation bandwidth $\delta\lambda/\lambda$	-	~20%
Spectrometer	Wavelength range	micron	1.0-1.7
	Spectral Resolution	-	≥ 40
	Typical observation bandwidth $\delta\lambda/\lambda$	-	~20%

NIR Channel Volume (green) on Optical Bench (yellow) with CCS_{NIR}

NIR Channel Input Beam Light Path

Input beam vector:

- Direction cosines
 - [0.8829, 0.4695, 0.0]
- Entrance pupil image
 - [538.8, 273.7, 105.5] mm

Context Views: EAC-5 Integrated Coronagraph Instrument

HWO TMPO Ultraviolet Multi-Object Spectrograph (UV MOS)

Design Assumptions & Guidelines

HWO TMPO UV MOS Team

April 2026

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Assumptions & Guidelines

- The UV MOS is intended to be a general-use, multi-object, ultraviolet and visible-light spectrograph with multiple modes:
 - FUV Imager (3' x 3' field of view)
 - FUV/NUV/Visible light MOS (3' x 3' field of view; 100 – 1000 nm; R~500 – 50K)
 - High-resolution point source spectroscopy (100 – 400 nm; R ≤ 100K)
- For EAC-5, the government team used **Instrument A** resources and interfaces for the UV MOS
- Initial study used the same gratings/bandpasses as LUMOS-B
- Accommodation Guidelines (preliminary):
 1. Volume
 - See slide 43
 2. Mass Allocation
 - 500 kg (slide 18)
 3. Power
 - 525 W (slide 20)

Initial UVMOS specifications

We used LUMOS-B gratings and bandpasses for initial optical design

Instrument Parameter	Units	G120M	G150M	G180M	G155L	G145LL	G165LL	G300M	G700L	FUV Imager
Optimized Spectral Bandpass	nm	100-140	130-170	160-200	100-200	100-200	110-200	200-400	400-1000	100-200
Actual Spectral Bandpass	nm	93-159	111-189	141-219	93-267	93-210	110-270	193-460	340-1000	100-200
Spectral Resolving Power ($\lambda/\Delta\lambda$) [Required]	-	3.0×10^4	3.0×10^4	3.0×10^4	8000	500	500	2.0×10^4	1.5×10^4	-

	Parameter	Value	Units
FUV Imager	Bandpass	100 - 200	nm
	Angular resolution	50	mas
	Field of view	3 x 3	arcmin x arcmin
	FUV Detector Temperature	220	K
	Filters	TBD	-
MOS	Bandpass	100 - 1000	nm
	Field of view	3 x 3	arcmin x arcmin
	Spectral resolving power	500 - 50,000	-
	Angular resolution	50	mas
	FUV Detector Temperature	220	K
	NUV/Visible Detector Temperature	170	K
	Microshutter Dimensions	100 x 200	$\mu\text{m} \times \mu\text{m}$
	Microshutter Array Format	384 x 768	- x -
MSA Buttability	2 x 2	- x -	
Point Source	Spectral resolving power	100,000	-
	Bandpass	100-400	nm
	FUV Detector Temperature	220	K
	NUV/Visible Detector Temperature	170	K
For all modes	# preceding reflections	4	-

Instrument A (or EAC-5 UV MOS) Optical feed from telescope

Instrument A (or EAC-5 UV MOS) Overview (dimensions next page)

NOTES: UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED

1. INTERFACE CONTROL DRAWING.
2. ALL DIMENSIONS ARE IN METRIC.
3. THIS IS A LIMITED DIMENSION DRAWING. THE ELECTRONIC PART FILE, "Instrument_A_w_for_UV", SHALL BE USED TO SUPPLEMENT THE DRAWING DATA.

Instrument A (or EAC-5 UV MOS) Dimensions

FOLD LINE

HWO TMPO High Resolution Imager

Government Concept Design Assumptions & Guidelines

HWO TMPO HRI Team

April 2026

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Assumptions & Guidelines

- HRI is intended to be a general-purposed, high-resolution camera for astrophysics and precision astrometry
- Configuration Assumptions made for EAC5 government designs:
 - HRI contains two different channels:
 - HRI-A: VIS Astrometry camera that also acts as a primary guiding instrument
 - HRI-S: Science + wavefront sensing and control channels
 - UVIS, including NUV
 - NIR
 - Enables secondary guiding capability
- For EAC-5, the government team used **Instrument B** resources and interfaces for HRI-S and **Instrument C** resources and interfaces for HRI-A
- Accommodation Guidelines (preliminary):
 1. Volume
 - Instrument B (HRI-S): Slide 52
 - Instrument C (HRI-A): Slide 54
 2. Mass
 - Instrument B: 350 kg
 - Instrument C: 350 kg
 - HRI-S + HRI-A: 700 kg
 3. Power
 - Instrument B: 250 W
 - Instrument C: 250 W
 - HRI-S + HRI-A: 500 W

Proof-of-concept for HRI

- Diffraction-limited wavelength: 500 nm
- Nyquist sample the core of the PSF
- 3' x 4' FOV (masses of exoplanets)

- Diffraction-limited wavelength: 550 nm
- Nyquist sample the the spatial resolution element at 550 nm
- 3' x 2' FOV (following HDI heritage)

- Diffraction-limited wavelength: 1.2 μm
- Nyquist sample the the spatial resolution element at 1.2 μm
- 3' x 2' FOV (following HDI heritage)

Guider functionality provides roll when combined with guiding in science channel.

NEA (tip/tilt) < 1 mas per axis at 10 Hz.

NEA (roll) < 1000 mas (requires ≥ 2 guide stars)

Wavefront sensing via defocusing lenses à la JWST

Initial HRI-A specifications

Configuration	Parameter	Value	Units	Comments
HRI-A	Field of View	3' x 4'	arcmin x arcmin	Note that this is currently shared with the guiding functionality
	Plate scale	5.3	mas/pix	Nyquist sample core at diffraction-limited wavelength
	Bandpass	400 - 1000	nm	
	Detector Temperature	170	K	
	# preceding reflections	4	-	From telescope
	f-number	38.9	-	
	Astrometric Precision per epoch	0.3	μ as	Likely necessitates detector calibration
	Diffraction-Limited wavelength	500	nm	

Initial HRI-S specifications

Configuration	Parameter	Value	Units	Comments
HRI-S, UVIS	Field of view	3' x 2'	arcmin x arcmin	
	Diffraction-Limited wavelength	500	nm	
	Bandpass	200 - 1000	nm	
	Plate scale	6.9	mas/pix	Nyquist sample spatial resolution element at diffraction-limited wavelength
	Detector temperature	170	K	
	f-number	16.4		
	Filters	TBD		
	Allowable wavefront error	≤ 35	nm RMS WFE	
# preceding reflections	4	-	From telescope	
HRI-S, NIR	Field of view	3' x 2'	arcmin x arcmin	
	Diffraction-Limited wavelength	1200	nm	
	Bandpass	1000 - 2500 (TBC)	nm	
	Plate scale	15.1	mas/pix	Nyquist sample spatial resolution element at diffraction-limited wavelength
	Detector temperature	95	K	
	f-number	13.7		
	Filters	TBD		
	Allowable wavefront error	≤ 71	nm RMS WFE	
# preceding reflections	4	-	From telescope	

Initial wavefront sensing specifications

Configuration	Parameter	Value	Units	Comments
Wavefront sensing, in either of the HRI-S channels	Wavefront sensing reference wavelength	632 or 1550	nm	
	Wavefront sensing sampling "Q"	≥ 1.25 at reference wavelength	-	$Q = \lambda * f\text{-number} / \text{pixel pitch}$
	Wavefront sensing defocus ranges	$-8\lambda, -4\lambda, 0\lambda, 4\lambda, 8\lambda$	-	
	Wavefront sensing spectral bandpass	20% of reference wavelength		
	Wavefront sensing focus sweep speed	≤ 10	minutes	
	Pupil Imaging resolution	≤ 2	mm	At telescope entrance pupil
	Number of pupil wheel element spaces	≥ 3		

Suggest having WFS operational in both channels if possible.

Initial guiding specifications

- 2 Degrees of freedom measured (tip + tilt) with the goal to include roll
- Noise equivalent angle (NEA) < 1 mas, per axis for tip + tilt; < 1000 mas for roll
- Guide star availability $\geq 95\%$ (TBC)
- Number of stars to be found ≥ 10 (TBC)
- Field of view: 3' x 4' (TBC)
- Able to acquire guide stars in the presence of ≤ 200 mas (per axis of tip, tilt, and roll) of pointing error
- Guider sampling rate of 5 (TBR) - 10 Hz
- Wavelength range of 400 – 1000 nm
- Wavefront error input to FGS < 35 nm RMS

Instrument B (or EAC-5 HRI-S) Optical feed from telescope

Instrument B (or EAC-5 HRI-S) Overview *(dimensions next page)*

Instrument B (or EAC-5 HRI-S) Dimensions

NOTES: UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED

1. INTERFACE CONTROL DRAWING.
2. ALL DIMENSIONS ARE IN METRIC.
3. THIS IS A LIMITED DIMENSION DRAWING. THE ELECTRONIC PART FILE, "Instrument_B", SHALL BE USED TO SUPPLEMENT THE DRAWING DATA.

DETAIL B
SCALE 1/5

ISO VIEW
FOR REFERENCE ONLY

FOLD LINE

A

D

C

B

A

4

3

2

FOLD LINE

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Instrument C (or EAC-5 HRI-A) Overview *(dimensions next page)*

NOTES: UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED

- 1. INTERFACE CONTROL DRAWING
- 2. ALL DIMENSIONS ARE IN METRIC
- 3. THIS IS A LIMITED DIMENSION DRAWING. THE ELECTRONIC PART FILE, "Instrument_C", SHALL BE USED TO SUPPLEMENT THE DRAWING DATA.

Instrument C (or EAC-5 HRI-A) Dimensions

DETAIL C
SCALE 1/5

ISO VIEW
FOR REFERENCE ONLY

FOLD LINE

HWO TMPO Ultraviolet Integral Field Spectrograph (UV IFS)

Design Assumptions & Guidelines

HWO TMPO UV IFS Team

April 2026

H A B I T A B L E
W R L D S
O B S E R V A T O R Y

The logo for the Habitable Worlds Observatory (HWO) is positioned in the bottom-right corner. It consists of the words "HABITABLE", "WORLD S", and "OBSERVATORY" stacked vertically in a light blue, spaced-out, sans-serif font. A stylized white arc, representing a celestial body or orbit, is placed between the "W" and "R" of "WORLD S".

Assumptions & Guidelines

- The UV-IFS is intended to sample the diffraction limited angular resolution of the telescope + instrument to deliver moderate spectral resolution data cubes (x,y,λ) over an equally modest field of view ($\sim 3\text{-}5$ arcseconds). Science drivers currently target the ultraviolet, but some emerging science cases may drive this into the visible band.
 - Ultraviolet (100 – 400 nm) integral field spectrograph with high angular resolution (20 mas) and moderate spectral resolution ($R \sim 4000$) over a ~ 3 arcsecond square field of view
- For EAC-5, the government team used **Instrument D** resources and interfaces for the UV-IFS
- Accommodation Guidelines (preliminary):
 1. Volume
 - See Slide 62
 2. Mass
 - 200 kg
 3. Power
 - 200 W

Initial UVIFS specifications

Parameter	Value	Units
Bandpass	100 - 400	nm
Field of view	3" x (1.5-3)"	arcsec x arcsec
Angular Resolution	20	mas
Spectral Resolving Power	4000	-
FUV Detector Temperature	220	K
NUV Detector Temperature	170	K
Spot size	15	mas
Number of Resols/Spectra	76-152	-
Image Slicer Facet Width	~80	microns

Instrument D (or EAC-5 UVIFS) Optical feed from telescope

EAC-5 UV IFS Optical Layout

Instrument D (or UV IFS) Overview *(dimensions next page)*

NOTES: UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED

1. INTERFACE CONTROL DRAWING.
2. ALL DIMENSIONS ARE IN METRIC.
3. THIS IS A LIMITED DIMENSION DRAWING. THE ELECTRONIC PART FILE, "Instrument_D", SHALL BE USED TO SUPPLEMENT THE DRAWING DATA.

Instrument D (or UV-IFS) Dimensions

DETAIL D
SCALE 1/5

SECTION D-D

ISO VIEW
FOR REFERENCE ONLY

FOLD LINE

A

4

3

2

1

REV 03/2024

HWO TMPO Extra Instrument (XI)

Design Assumptions & Guidelines

H A B I T A B L E
W R L D S
O B S E R V A T O R Y

The logo for the Habitable Worlds Observatory (HWO) is positioned in the bottom-right corner. It consists of the words "HABITABLE", "WORLDS", and "OBSERVATORY" stacked vertically in a light blue, spaced-out, sans-serif font. A stylized white symbol, resembling a crescent moon or a partial arc, is placed between the "W" and "R" of "WORLDS".

Assumptions & Guidelines

- The Extra Instrument (XI) is reserved for additional instrument candidates, including a NUV Coronagraph, UV Spectropolarimeter, and others
- For EAC-5, the government team did not develop a concept for **Instrument E** but has provided preliminary mass, power, and volume allocations
- Accommodation Guidelines (preliminary):
 1. Volume
 - See slide 66
 2. Mass
 - 200 kg
 3. Power
 - 200 W

Instrument E Overview *(dimensions next page)*

NOTES: UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED

1. INTERFACE CONTROL DRAWING
2. ALL DIMENSIONS ARE IN METRIC
3. THIS IS A LIMITED DIMENSION DRAWING. THE ELECTRONIC PART FILE, "Instrument_E", SHALL BE USED TO SUPPLEMENT THE DRAWING DATA.

Instrument E (or XI) Dimensions

FOLD LINE

BACK-UP

1. Discussion: Unobstructed Freeform Telescopes

- Unlike “Off-axis” designs of rotationally symmetric systems, the telescope design for EAC5 is better described as “unobstructed” since the mirrors are defined about the central ray through the system, known as the “base ray,” and tilt with respect to this ray is applied to the mirrors to remove obstruction between reflections, as shown in the drawing below for EAC5.
- The telescope is not rotationally symmetric. All mirrors are defined as an XY Polynomial series (to 6th order), and plane symmetry is enforced. For some instruments, dedicated fold mirrors are fully asymmetric and use higher order polynomial coefficients to help correct the telescope image interface at the instrument.

2. Design Driver: Minimize number of reflections for UV instruments

- **UV science is benefitted by having a minimum # of reflections to detection, which allows maximum throughput and sensitivity.**
- **The ideal placement of UV MOS is separated laterally from the primary mirror, not tucked behind it. Requiring instruments to be behind the Primary necessitates additional fold mirrors.**
- **A better location for both UV MOS and for CI would be between the primary and secondary mirrors, but mechanical packaging prohibits this location.**

2. Design Driver: Flat Field required for UVI MOS MSA

- **The UVI MOS Micro-Shutter Array (MSA) requires a flat image from the telescope, since it currently cannot be fabricated with a spherical shape.**
- **This flat field constraint is similar to that of the Roman Space Telescope wide field channel, where the detector is placed at the telescope focus.**
- **This flat field constraint is fundamentally different than JWST, however, as JWST had a curved image surface with a radius of curvature equal to the exit pupil distance from the Fine Steering Mirror (FSM), which provided observatory level pointing control.**
- **EAC5 requires a 3rd fold mirror to access the instrument location required for UVI MOS due to packaging constraints. Also, the larger MSA can be tiled with small tilts to better tolerate residual field curvature.**
- **Finally, it should be noted that since the UVI MOS drives the design of M1 and M2 to have an optimized image at the MSA, less optimal image quality result at the interfaces to the other instruments, but any additional mirrors in the path can help control degradation by applying freeform surface corrections.**

2. Design Driver: Match focal length to UVI MOS needs

- The telescope focal length (plate scale) is current set by the physical size of the UV MOS MSA and its desired field of view on the sky.
- This is a first-order system constraint that effectively controls the curvature at M1 and M2
- **EAC5**
 - MSA Size = 150 x 150 mm, with slit aperture pitch of 100 x 200 microns
 - FOV: 3 x 3 arcmin
 - Focal Length = 171 meters

2. Design Driver: Angle of Incidence for Polarization Aberrations

	Delta AOI			
	EAC1	EAC2	EAC3	EAC5
M1	11.36	11.19	11.08	12.84
M2	12.82	12.83	11.88	12.84
	ΔAOI in degrees			

- Polarization aberration modeling is required for HWO, to evaluate the impact on the Coronagraph Instrument (CI) yield performance metric.
- Currently our design strategy to manage these aberrations is to minimize the “delta-AOI” on the telescope optics that feed the CI
- Delta-AOI is defined as the difference in angle of incidence at each mirror (i.e. max – min value).
- Minimizing delta-AOI effectively constrains the F/# of the primary mirror to be greater than ~F/2.5 or so, which pushes M2 further away from M1.
- The goal is to keep delta-AOI under 15 degrees, but impact requires a full optical analysis.

Reducing Radiator Blackbody Sink Temperatures

- **If radiator sink temperatures are close to an instrument component temperature:**
 - Reduce the delta temperature from the component to the radiator
 - Increase radiator area
 - Consider warmer detectors
- **Use instrument level architecture to reduce sink temperatures (i.e. reduce sunshade IR backloading)**
 - Baffles can be optimized using parabolic shaped vanes or other similar concepts
 - Expect a significant difference between physical radiator area and effective area due to reduced view to space
 - For instance, a 4m² radiator may only have a 2m² effective area
 - Additional deployable shields may block other instrument radiators views to space and may violate prescribed instrument volumes defined in the mechanical interface guidance

Notional Directional Baffles on Radiator

Recommended Thermal Considerations

- **The instrument bays will be surrounded on 5 sides with a room temperature environment → may need to create thermal zones for other temperature components**
- **If the radiator blackbody sink temperature isn't significantly colder than the components rejecting the heat, expect the thermal design to be more complex**
 - Parasitic heat loads will require close management
 - Active cooling may be necessary
- **Place cold detectors close to radiators**
- **Parasitic heat loads (heat transfer from warmer areas to colder areas) will heavily drive thermal architecture**
 - Parasitic heat loads in low temperature components can sometimes represent 90%+ of the total rejected heat loads
 - To estimate these loads where cryogenic temperatures are concerned, consider using this paper as a reference:
 - Ross, R. G. Jr. (2004). Estimation of thermal conduction loads for structural supports of cryogenic spacecraft assemblies. *Cryogenics*, 44(6–8), 421–424. doi:10.1016/j.cryogenics.2004.02.019
 - Describes a nested “shell” configuration that can be used to minimize parasitic heat loads
 - Transporting heat at cold temperatures is not the same as near room temperature
 - Consider delta temperatures from your cold components to the radiator, as well as potential heat leaks to these transport components (i.e. heat pipes, high purity bars)
 - Heat pipes require working fluids in certain temperature regimes. Before assuming heat pipe architecture, ensure there is a working fluid or material that is best suited to your needs
 - In pre-phase A, margins are in the 50%-100% range for low temperature components due to parasitic uncertainty
 - Consider if active cooling is an option

Warmer detectors will significantly simplify the mechanical and thermal architecture